

Graceful Labeling of Chain Graphs with Pendants

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ABSTRACT

Graph labeling is one of the most popular research areas in graph theory. There is a vast amount of literature available on graph labeling. In this research, we especially concentrate on a special type of graph labeling method called vertex graceful labeling. A simple connected graph G is said to be a vertex graceful if there exists a vertex graceful labeling on the vertices of G starting from 1. *Graceful labeling* of G is a vertex labeling f , which is defined as an injective mapping from $V(G)$ to $[0, |E(G)|]$ such that the edge labeling $f_v: E(G) \rightarrow [1, |E(G)|]$ defined by $f_v(uv) = |f(u) - f(v)|$ is also injective. There is a very famous open conjecture in this area abbreviated as GTC which stands for graceful tree conjecture or Ringel - Kotzig conjecture which hypothesizes that all trees are graceful. In this research work, we introduce graceful labeling for a chain of the key graph with a finite number of pendants and a chain of linear dice graphs with a finite number of pendants.

Keywords: *Graceful labeling, Key graph, Linear dice graph*

1. INTRODUCTION

Graceful Labeling is a famous graph labeling method and is an active research area in graph theory. This labeling method was introduced by Alexander Rosa in 1967 and was originally given the name β -labeling (Rosa, A. (1967) *On Certain*

Valuations of the Vertices of a Graph. Theory of Graphs (International Symposium, Rome, July 1966), Dunod Gordon & Breach Science Publishers, Inc., New York, and Dunod Paris, 349-355. - References - Scientific Research Publishing, n.d.). There are two main types of graceful labeling as vertex graceful labeling and edge graceful labeling. Over the past 50 years, many graphs have been proven to be graceful and recent work on graceful labeling includes linear dice graphs and path-dice graphs (Abdul Kader et al., 2014). In our work, we introduce general graceful labeling for a chain of linear dice graphs with a finite number of pendants and a chain of the key graph with a finite number of pendants with some limitations under Theorem 1 and Theorem 2. Applications of cycle graphs are very much popular in communication networks, and since these graphs represent a chain of cycles, we strongly believe that these graphs also can be used to model computer networks.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section will be given the basic information to continue our work.

Preliminaries

So, we will introduce some fundamental definitions first.

Definition 1: Graceful Labeling.

Let $G = G(V, E)$ be a graph with $m = |E(G)|$, where $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ denote the set of vertices and edges, respectively. Graceful labeling of G is

a vertex labeling $f: V \rightarrow [0, m]$ such that f is injective, and the edge labeling $f_e: E \rightarrow [1, m]$ defined by $f_e(uv) = |f(u) - f(v)|$ is also injective. Such a graph is called a *graceful graph*.

Definition 2: Chain of linear dice graph.

This graph is constituted of a chain of C_4 graphs in which among two consecutive dices there is a common vertex and each C_4 is termed as dice (Abdul Kader et al., 2014).

Definition 3: Chain of linear dice graph with pendants.

Here we consider the above linear dice chain with at least one edge (pendant) at each vertex of the C_4 as in Figure 1.

Definition 4: Chain of the key graph.

This graph can be considered as a derivation of a linear dice chain. Let's consider a linear dice, one of its four vertices connected to an edge that looks like a key, and let it be the main block. Then this graph is designed as a chain of the above block so that any consecutive two dices have one common edge.

Definition 5: Chain of the key graph with pendants

Here we consider the above chain of the key graphs with at least one edge (pendant) at each vertex of the C_4 as in Figure 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theorem 1

Linear dice graph is graceful with a finite number of pendants; $m_i \geq 1$.

Figure 40: Chain of linear dice graph with pendants

$$f(U_1) = |E| = \sum_{i=1}^{3n+1} m_i + 4n \quad (1)$$

$$f(U_i) = f(W_{i-1, m_{3(i-1)}}) - 1; i = 2, 3, \dots \quad (2)$$

$$f(U_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} j - 1; & \left\{ \begin{matrix} i - 1 \\ j - 1, 2, 3, \dots, m_1 \end{matrix} \right. \\ f(V_{i-1}) + j; & \left\{ \begin{matrix} i - 2, 3, \dots \\ j - 1, 2, 3, \dots, m_{3i-2} \end{matrix} \right. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$f(W_i) = f(U_{i, m_{3i-2}}) + 1; i = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (4)$$

$$f(W_{i,j}) = f(V_{i, m_{3i-1}}) - 1 - j; \left\{ \begin{matrix} i - 1, 3, \dots \\ j - 1, 2, \dots, m_{3i} \end{matrix} \right. \quad (5)$$

$$f(V_i) = f(W_i) + 1; i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

$$f(V_{i,j}) = f(U_i) - j; \left\{ \begin{matrix} i - 1, 2, 3, \dots \\ j - 1, 2, 3, \dots, m_{3i-1} \end{matrix} \right. \quad (7)$$

Using Eq. (1), $f(U_1)$ can be calculated. Then using Eq. (3), we can calculate $f(U_{i,j})$ values for the first block. Then using Eq. (4), $f(W_i)$ can be calculated for $i = 1$ and using Eq. (6), $f(V_i)$ can be calculated for $i = 1$. By using the $f(U_1)$ value and Eqs. (5) and (7) we can calculate $f(W_{i,j})$, $f(V_{i,j})$ values for the first block. Finally using Eq. (2), $f(U_2)$ can be calculated.

In each block first, we label the node U_i first, then we use that label to get the pendant values of the $V_{i,j}$, $W_{i,j}$. $U_{i,j}$ values for $i > 1$ will be calculated using the previous block's V_i value and So, likewise repeating the above procedure we can get the rest of the labels easily.

Theorem 2

Chain of the key graph is graceful for a finite number of pendants; $m_i \geq 1$.

Figure 41: Chain of key graph

$$f(X_0) = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$f(U_1) = |E| = \sum_{i=1}^{4n} m_i + 5n; m_i \geq 1 \quad (9)$$

$$f(X_i) = \begin{cases} f(W_{i,m_{4i-1}}) - 1; & i = 1,3,5,\dots,n \\ f(W_{i,m_{4i-1}}) + 1; & i = 2,4,\dots,n-1 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$f(U_i) = \begin{cases} f(X_{i-1,m_{4(i-1)}}) + 1; & i = 2,4,\dots \\ f(X_{i-1,m_{4(i-1)}}) - 1; & i = 1,3,\dots \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$f(V_i) = \begin{cases} f(W_i) + 1; & i = 1,3,5,\dots,n \\ f(W_i) - 1; & i = 2,4,\dots,n-1 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

$$f(W_i) = \begin{cases} f(U_{i,m_{4i-3}}) + 1; & i = 1,3,5,\dots \\ f(U_{i,m_{4i-3}}) - 1; & i = 2,4,\dots \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$f(U_{i+1,j}) = \begin{cases} f(X_i) + j; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 0,2,4,\dots \\ j = 1,2,\dots,m_{4i+1} \end{array} \right. \\ f(X_i) - j; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 1,3,5,\dots \\ j = 1,2,\dots,m_{4i+1} \end{array} \right. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

$$f(V_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} f(U_i) - j; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 1,3,\dots \\ j = 1,2,\dots,m_{4i-2} \end{array} \right. \\ f(U_i) + j; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 2,4,\dots \\ j = 1,2,\dots,m_{4i-2} \end{array} \right. \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$f(W_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} f(V_{i,m_{4i-2}}) - 1 - j; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 1,3,\dots \\ j = 1,2,\dots,m_{4i-1} \end{array} \right. \\ f(V_{i,m_{4i-2}}) + 1 + j; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 2,4,\dots \\ j = 1,2,\dots,m_{4i-1} \end{array} \right. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

$$f(X_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} f(V_i) + j; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 1,3,\dots \\ j = 1,2,\dots,m_{4j} \end{array} \right. \\ f(V_i) - j; & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = 2,4,\dots \\ j = 1,2,\dots,m_{4j} \end{array} \right. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

As I have mentioned, the first label X_0 as 0 and U_1 as the total number of edges using Eq. (8) and Eq. (9) respectively. Using Eq. (14) we can compute $f(U_{1,j})$ values for $i = 0$ then, applying these values to Eqs. (12) and (13) we can calculate $f(V_i)$ and $f(W_i)$. As usually in Figure 2, $f(V_{i,j})$ and $f(W_{i,j})$ values can be calculated for the first block using $f(U_1)$ value using Eqs. (15) and (16). Using the $f(V_1)$, we can compute $f(X_{i,j})$ using Eq. (17). Using Eqs. (11) and (17), $f(U_i)$ can be calculated for $i > 1$. Using the $f(W_{i,j})$ value and Eq. (10), we can get $f(X_i)$ value too.

Likewise, we can get the labels for the other blocks by repeating this procedure.

Now, we illustrate Theorem 1 & 2 by using the following examples given under Figure 3 & Figure 4 respectively.

Figure 42: Graceful labeling of a chain of linear dice graph with a finite number of pendants

Figure 43: Graceful labeling of a chain of the key graph with pendants

3. CONCLUSION

In our research, we discussed the vertex graceful labeling of a chain of the key graph with a finite number of pendants and a chain of linear dice graph with a finite number of pendants. Under two theorems, we have given the method of construction of the two graphs and the existence of the gracefulfulness of some arbitrary graphs obtained for different n and m_i values and verified that they are graceful.

4. REFERENCES

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